

An unexpected new *Oestophora* species from Picos de Urbión, Iberian Peninsula (Pulmonata: Trissexodontidae)

Una inesperada nueva especie de *Oestophora* de Picos de Urbión, península Ibérica (Pulmonata: Trissexodontidae)

Carlos E. PRIETO*, Oscar ARRIBAS**, María José MADEIRA*** & Benjamín J. GÓMEZ-MOLINER***

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ABSTRACT

Oestophora urbionensis, a new species from Duruelo de la Sierra, on southwestern slopes of Sierra de Urbión (between La Rioja and Soria provinces, Spain) is described. Judging from the shell, it is very similar to *O. silvae* Ortiz de Zárate López, 1962 and anatomical differentiation is mainly based on the greater length of dart sac complex, free oviduct and mucous glands. A molecular analysis based on COI confirms the taxonomical validity of both species, which show a closer relationship with *O. lusitanica* (Pfeiffer, 1841) than with other congeners. This *lusitanica* species-group was known so far from northwestern Iberia and Cantabrian Mountains and now is found to extend to the North Iberian System.

RESUMEN

Se describe *Oestophora urbionensis*, una nueva especie procedente de Duruelo de la Sierra, en las laderas suroccidentales de la Sierra de Urbión (entre las provincias de La Rioja y Soria, España). A juzgar por la concha, es muy similar a *O. silvae* Ortiz de Zárate, 1962 y la diferenciación anatómica se basa principalmente en la mayor longitud del complejo del saco del dardo, el oviducto libre y las glándulas mucosas. Un análisis molecular basado en COI confirma la validez taxonómica de ambas especies, que muestran una relación estrecha con *O. lusitanica* (Pfeiffer, 1841). Este grupo *lusitanica* estaba restringido hasta ahora al noroeste de Iberia y las montañas del Cantábrico y ahora se encuentra que se extiende hasta el Sistema Ibérico del Norte.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oestophora* Hesse 1907 belongs to the family Trissexodontidae, a near endemic Iberian taxon (ARRÉBOLA ET AL. 2006) (Iberomaghrebian, formerly western Mediterranean, if fossil records are correctly attributed)

with a short but disputed history. NORD-SIECK (1987) erected Trissexodontini, together with Oestophorini and Caracollinini, as tribes of the subfamily Ciliellinae (Hygromiidae); SCHILEYKO (1991) raised them to subfamilial rank

* Departamento de Zoología y Biología Celular Animal, Facultad de Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad del País Vasco, Apdo. 644, 48080-Bilbao (Spain) [carlos.prieto@ehu.es]

** Ntra. Sra. de Calatañazor 17 B, 42004 Soria (Spain) [oarribas@xtec.cat]

*** Departamento de Zoología y Biología Celular Animal, Facultad de Farmacia, Universidad del País Vasco, Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain) [benjamin.gomez@ehu.es]

within the family Helicodontidae, which included also the new subfamilies Gittenbergeriinae and Lindholmiolinae. PRIETO ET AL. (1993) segregated the Trissexodontinae, Oestophorinae and Caracollininae together as a distinct family with respect to Helicodontidae, and considered that a subfamilial division was inappropriate. BANK ET AL. (2001) followed this statement, but molecular analyses recovered those taxa as tribes of the subfamily Trissexodontinae (GÓMEZ-MOLINER ET AL. 2013; RAZKIN ET AL. 2015), leaving Oestophorini monotypic and suggesting the division of *Oestophora* into two species groups, dentate and edentate species.

ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE (1962) and PUENTE (1996b) have reviewed the genus *Oestophora*. It is speciose, comprising more than a dozen of indubitable species distributed along a great part of the Iberian Peninsula, northern Morocco (AHUIR-GALINDO & TORRES-ALBA, 2017; PUENTE 1996; TORRES-ALBA & AHUIR-GALINDO, 2011) and in the Azores archipelago, where two supposedly allochthonous species have been recorded (BACKHUYS 1975). *Oestophora barrelsi* Hovestadt & Ripken, 2015 from the offshore Berlengas Islands is the last Iberian species added (HOVESTADT & RIPKEN, 2015). The first records of fossil *Oestophora* (s. l.?) appear from the lower Oligocene of Europe and NW Africa, and are also present in the lower Miocene of France (ZILCH 1960; REY 1974). As a Plio-Pleistocene fossil, *Oestophora* had a wider distribution being represented in Balearic islands by two fossil species, *Oestophora dentata* Paul 1984 from Ibiza and *Oestophora bellocerica* (Altaba 2007) from Majorca (PAUL 1984; ALTABA 2007). PAUL (1984) ascribed to *O. dentata* a fossil record from Sardinia (ESU 1978).

In a detailed study of dentate *Oestophora* species, HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2012) confirmed the validity of *O. barbella* (Servain, 1880), to which they ascribe all Spanish records published for *O. barbula* (Rossmässler, 1838) during more than a century, and restricted *O. barbula* to the western-

central part of Portugal. While most (seven) of the Iberian *Oestophora* are restricted to Andalusia, the northern part of the Iberian Peninsula is inhabited by three species, *O. barbella* and *O. lusitanica* (Pfeiffer, 1841) in Galicia and Asturias, and *O. silvae* Ortiz de Zárate, 1962 from Galicia to Bizkaia province. The finding of an isolated population of an *Oestophora* species belonging to the *lusitanica* group in the Picos de Urbión was surprising because it is the first record in the northern Sistema Ibérico, south of the Ebro valley, and noteworthy because it is from an area of crystalline rocks. Moreover, it is relatively well prospected area since the middle of XXth Century (PRIETO 1986; ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE 1991; ARRIBAS 1992; ALTONAGA ET AL. 1994, among others). Although externally it recalls *Oestophora silvae*, the dissection proved it is an undescribed new species.

MATERIAL & METHODS

Study area

The Picos de Urbión massif reaches its maximum altitude at 2228 m a.s.l. (Fig. 1). The Alpine orogeny deformed and fractured these materials, giving rise to a monoclinial relief. The massif was later affected by the Pleistocene glaciations, which left deep valleys of up to 6-7 km in length, moraines and other glacial deposits that descend down to 1270 m in the northern slope. The deep basins of lakes such as those of the Laguna Negra, Laguna de Urbión, Laguna Helada or Laguna Larga are also well known to have resulted from glacial scouring (GARCÍA-RUIZ ET AL. 1998). The area is composed mainly of quartzite or quartzite microconglomerates and red clays and limestones of the Upper Jurassic and Early Cretaceous, corresponding to a large paleodelta (TISCHER 1966) (Fig. 2).

According to RIVAS-MARTÍNEZ (1987), Urbión Massif presents an Atlantic or Ibero-Atlantic flora, lying within the Carpetane-Iberian-Leonese province (Soriano-Iberian sector). The

Figure 1. Perspective view (Google Earth) of the southern slope of Sierra de Urbión from Duruelo de la Sierra. Figure 2. Geologic map of the area shown in Figure 1 (matched maps use different colors). Source, MAGNA50, (mapas 278 & 316, Instituto Geológico y Minero de España) [from top to bottom: sandstones (Upper Jurassic), Neocomian conglomerates and gravels and Aptian gravels, sands and clays (Lower Cretaceous). Red arrow shows the type locality of *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp.

Figura 1. Perspectiva (Google Earth) de la ladera sur de la Sierra de Urbión desde Duruelo de la Sierra. Figura 2. Mapa geológico del área mostrada en la Figura 1 (ambos mapas usan distintos colores). Fuente, MAGNA50, (mapas 278 & 316, Instituto Geológico y Minero de España) [de arriba abajo: areniscas (Jurásico superior), conglomerados y gravas del Neocomiense y gravas, arenas y arcillas del Aptiano (Cretácico inferior). La flecha roja muestra la localidad tipo de *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp.

location of the studied *Oestophora* is in the lower limit of the Oromediterranean vegetation belt (from 1500 to the upper limit of the forest, about 1850 to 2050 m in this the area, GARCÍA DE CELIS, ARROYO-PÉREZ & GANDÍA-FERNÁNDEZ, 2008), characterized by mountain coniferous forests of *Pinus sylvestris*, with a subhumid ombroclima (precipitations greater than 1200 mm, and even probably above 1500-1600 mm in the mountain crests, according to the estimations of ARNÁEZ-VADILLO 1987). The frost-free period is less than 50 days per year and late-lying snow-patches remain on the ground for more than 7 months per year (ARRIBAS 1994). The only available climatic data come from observatories located on the southern slopes of the massif, between 1100 and 1150 m altitude, with an average record of 9.6°C in

Vinuesa for the period 1990-2001. The average temperature in the mountain area would be below 8°C (4 to 8°C) following GARCÍA DE CELIS ET AL. (2008).

The vegetation series (Fig. 3) correspond to the acidophilous Oromediterranean Series of the scots pine with broom (with *Pinus sylvestris*, and occasionally with substitution thickets with *Cytisus oromediterraneus*, *Calluna vulgaris*, *Genista florida*, etc.) (SEGURA-ZUBIZARRETA, MATEO & BENITO-ALONSO 2012).

Specimens studied

Specimens were drowned in tapwater and then preserved in 70° ethanol. Animals were dissected and studied using an optical stereomicroscope with camera lucida (®Nikon SMZ-10), which was used for drawings of genital

Figure 3. Type locality of *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp., exact place where the first specimens were found; Scots pine forest with ferns interspersed among big sandstone blocks. Figure 4. A living specimen (9.95 mm in diameter) on a lichen-covered stone (*Rhizocarpon* sp.).

Figura 3. Localidad tipo de *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp., lugar exacto donde se encontraron los primeros especímenes; bosque de pino rojo con helechos intercalados entre grandes bloques de arenisca. Figura 4. Un espécimen vivo (9,95 mm de diámetro) sobre una piedra cubierta de líquenes (*Rhizocarpon* sp.).

systems. Radulae were studied and drawn with microscopes @Nikon Optiphot and photos and measures were obtained with a stereomicroscope @Nikon DS 5M with digital camera and image analysis tools.

Genetic analyses

DNA extraction, PCR amplification and sequencing. Genomic DNA was extracted from a piece of foot using the DNeasy Tissue kit (Qiagen, Valencia, CA, USA) following the manufacturer's guidelines. Two mitochondrial genes, the cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (COI) and 16S RNA ribosomal subunit (16S), were selected for molecular analyses. PCR conditions for DNA amplification were as follow for all fragments: 96°C for 1 min, 35x (96°C for 30 s, 55°C for 30 s, 72°C for 1 min) and 72°C for 10 min. PCR products were purified and sequenced at Macrogen Inc using ABI3730XL or ABI3700 sequencer. All new sequences were deposited in GenBank (see Appendix S1 for primers and GenBank accession numbers).

Phylogenetic inference. The sequence alignments for the individual gene regions were performed using the online version of mafft 7 (KATO ET AL.

2002) with the default settings. The Q-INS-i algorithm was applied to the 16S rRNA and the 'auto' strategy was used for the COI data. Bayesian Inference (BI) phylogenetic analyses were performed on the concatenated dataset. The dataset was partitioned by genes, further dividing COI into three partitions according to codon positions. The best evolutionary models fitting each partition were selected applying the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (AKAIKE 1974) as implemented in jModelTest v.2.1.6 (DARRIBA ET AL. 2012). MrBayes v.3.2.7 (RONQUIST ET AL. 2012) was used to conduct BI analysis running it for 20x106 generations with a 25% burn-in value. MrBayes analyses were implemented at CIPRES Science Gateway (MILLER, PFEIFFER & SCHWARTZ 2010). The species *Caracollina lenticula* (Michaud, 1831) and *Trissexodon constrictus* (Boubée, 1836) were used as outgroups. A final concatenated data set with 1041 aligned characters was obtained for 22 individuals. Detailed information about the sequences of each gene and the complete dataset (sequence length, selected substitution models and their parameters) is summarized in Supplementary S2.

Figure 5. *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp. Holotype. Three views of the shell, and detail of the protoconch.
Figura 5. Oestophora urbionensis n. sp. Holotipo. Tres vistas de la concha y detalle del protoconcha.

TAXONOMY

Family TRISSEXODONTIDAE Nordsieck 1987

Genus *Oestophora* Hesse 1907

Oestophora urbionensis Prieto & Arribas n. sp.

Type material: Holotype, a fixed complete specimen, dissected; 20/09/1991, O. Arribas leg. Paratypes: 1 shell; 15/08/1991, O. Arribas leg. 3 snails + 14 shells (11 damaged or subadult); 20/09/1991, O. Arribas leg. 3 snails + 7 shells (4 damaged); 28/08/2006, O. Arribas leg. 3 snails (subadult) + 10 shells (2 subadult); 17/10/2010, C. Prieto leg. Holotype (MNCN15.05/200084) and Paratypes (MNCN15.05/200085-200088) stored in the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid, Spain).

Type locality: "El Castroviejo", 4 km North from Duruelo de la Sierra (Picos de Urbión massif, province of Soria, Spain); MGRS coordinates: 30TWM065485, 1540 m a.s.l.

Etymology: The specific epithet refers to the Picos de Urbión, the mountain chain where the described species was discovered.

Diagnosis: An edentate species of *Oestophora* with lenticular shell, light brown in color and weakly calcified. Light callus behind the upper part of the peristome. Genital apparatus with a dart sac complex longer and more

robust than in *O. silvae*, with bent epipallus nearly as long as the penis half-length.

External morphology (Figs. 4-6): Shell very depressed, more convex below than above. Spire nearly flat with 5-5 ½

Figure 6. *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp. Three views of the shell aperture of a paratype. Note the protuberance on the supracarinal area behind the aperture.

Figura 6. Oestophora urbionensis n. sp. Tres vistas de la apertura de la concha de un paratipo. Nótese la protuberancia en el área supracarinal detrás de la abertura.

convex whorls and slow and regular growth. Body whorl somewhat wider than the previous one, with rounded carinal angle in superior position, not descending towards the aperture. Umbilicus wide and perspective, $1/5$ to $1/4$ of shell diameter, and deep, leaving visible the internal winding. Apex flat; protoconch formed by $1\frac{1}{2}$ whorls. A somewhat oblique shell aperture, with shape of a crescent and narrow moon, extended forward at the top. Marginal edges widely separated and little converging. Columellar edge short and oblique, reflected over the umbilicus. Peristome whitish, thick and reflexed (except in the supracarinal zone), with acute and sinuous edge (seen from below). Without inner lip but a whitish zone can be seen in the upper parietal zone. Shell thin and light brown in color. Shell surface with a very fine periostracal regular granulation, a faint wavy spiral striation (more visible where the periostracum is lost) and rounded ribs (5-6 per mm in the body whorl) regularly distanced, weaker in the umbilical side; on the upper side, the spiral striation can be seen as resembling the weaving of a basket. Protoconch smooth at first $1/2$ whorl, followed by a spiral striation (10-11 striae) along the next whorl that transforms to granulation in the transi-

tion to teleoconch. Body grayish, darker in the upper parts.

External measurements (n=10) [min-max (average \pm std Error); in mm]. Shell diameter, 9.95-11.64 (10.75 \pm 0.58); shell height, 4.42-5.46 (4.83 \pm 0.32); umbilicus, 2.17-2.75 (2.35 \pm 0.18); height/diameter, 0.43-0.47 (0.45 \pm 0.01); diameter/umbilicus, 4.23-4.86 (4.59 \pm 0.17). Whorls number, 4.9-5.5 (5.2 \pm 0.18).

Genital morphology (Figs. 7, 8): Atrium short and cylindrical. Penis long, but shorter than vagina and free oviduct together, and as wide as the vaginal duct; penis/epiphallus border not evident. The penial retractor muscle sheathes the distal half of the epiphallus. Epiphallus folded in half, without any evidence of flagellum. Duct of the vas deferens relatively thick, widening conspicuously toward the spermoviduct. Vagina cylindrical, with the dart sac complex located along its middle third and being twice as thick as the vagina. Dart sac (presumably with a hooked dart inside; unseen) indistinct and small, but distal end indicated by a small notch near the base, and widely fused to the thick, muscular accessory sac, which is linked to a muscular ligament running from the vagina/accessory sac angle to the proximal part of the deferent duct (removed in Figs. 7, 8).

Figure 7. *Oestophora urbionensis* n.sp., distal genital system of a paratype. Pins have been digitally removed. Figure 8. *O. urbionensis* n.sp., genital apparatus morphology. Abbreviations, a: atrium; as: accessory sac; bc: bursa copulatrix; bcd: bursa copulatrix duct; ds: dart sac; e: epiphallus; fo: free oviduct; mg: mucous glands; p: penis; pn: penial nerve; rm: retractor muscle; so: spermooviduct; v: vagina; vd: vas deferens.

Figura 7. *Oestophora urbionensis* n.sp., aparato genital distal de un paratipo. Los alfileres se han eliminado digitalmente. Figura 8. *O. urbionensis* n.sp., morfología del aparato genital. Abreviaturas, a: atrio; as: saco accesorio; bc: bolsa copulatrix; bcd: conducto de la bolsa copulatrix; ds: saco del dardo; e: epifalo; fo: oviducto libre; mg: glándulas mucosas; p: pene; pn: nervio penial; rm: músculo retractor; so: espermooviducto; v: vagina; vd: conducto deferente.

Three long, slightly widened and zig-zag contorted mucous glands, with narrow bases, arising around the middle part of proximal vagina. Bursa copulatrix fusiform, nearly as longer as its duct, which is slightly widened at outlet. Free oviduct wider and slightly shorter than the vagina, being progressively widened toward the spermooviduct. Spermooviduct without relevant features.

Ecological data: "El Castroviejo" is a unique place due to the characteristic erosion of its sandstone rocks that recalls the ruins of a castle ("Castro Viejo" means old castle in Spanish). The site has a recreational area, created to promote visits to the unusual rock formations. This can carry a danger of excessive human pressure in this small area. The arboreal vegetation is composed of *Pinus sylvestris* (90% coverage),

which is natural in this area and elevation. The undergrowth of the type locality is covered by bracken (*Pteridium aquilinum*), which gives an idea of a certain environmental moisture (Fig. 3). Sandy substrate results from the weathering of the sandstones of Upper Jurassic age (Malm) (IGME 1986) (Fig. 2). These ancient sandstones contain in their matrix along with clays, a variable amount of calcium carbonate that probably has importance in allowing the existence of *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp. in the area.

The harsh conditions of the type locality, at a considerable elevation and with late-lying patches of snow, with a small period of summer drought (in part edaphic, due to the porosity of sands derived from sandstone weathering), suggest that the species must live

partly underground in the crevices between the large blocks partially buried in the ground. The specimens found, were under quite sunken stones that together with other rocks that leave crevices among them, remain not far from the drainage gullies of the area, suggesting the presence of buried boulders and screes in the subsoil. Other nearby areas are much drier and sunny, with *Genistella sagittalis* as substitution scrub. The other snail species found was *Discus rotundatus* (1 ex, 28/08/2006 and 4 ex 20/09/1991).

Molecular data: A final concatenated dataset with 1041 aligned characters was obtained for two specimens of the proposed new species and 18 specimens of two *Oestophora* species, together with two trissexodontids used as outgroups, *Caracollina lenticula* and *Trissexodon constrictus* (Table I; Supplementary S2).

The phylogeny recovered by Bayesian inference on the concatenated mitochondrial dataset (Fig. 9) shows specimens distribution colored according to the main phylogroups obtained. Our results recovered four well supported clades. Group 1 is strongly supported (BI: 0.98) and comprises the *calpeana*-group species, identified as *O. mariae*, *O. ebria*, *O. prietoi*, *O. calpeana*

and *O. ortizi*, all of them restricted to Andalusia, although relationships among lineages within this group are not clear. Groups 2 and 3 are fully supported (BI: 0,96 and 1, respectively) and recover those species belonging to the *lusitanica*-group, sampled from the northwestern part of Iberia and Cantabrian mountains. Group 2 is further divided into three supported sister clades for *O. silvae* and *O. urbionensis* n. sp., with two of them for *O. silvae* specimens, differentiating clearly those specimens collected from Galicia (BI:1), which properly belong to *O. silvae* s. str., from those collected in Asturias and Cantabria (BI:1), which hereafter are referred to as *Oestophora* sp. B. Group 3 is fully supported (BI:1) and contain *O. lusitanica* specimens from Galicia and the northern half of Portugal. Finally, the strongly supported group 4 (BI:1) comprises the *barbula*-group and turns out to be the sister group of the remaining *Oestophora* spp. (BI:0,93), although only specimens referable to *O. barbella* have been analyzed. This species, recently revalidated by HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK (2012), shows the wide distribution previously attributed to *O. barbula*, which consequently has a narrower distribution restricted to Central Portugal (HOLYOAK & HOLYOAK, 2012).

DISCUSSION

The generic allocation of *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp. does not present any doubt since the generic diagnostic characters are present in the new species (lenticular and umbilicated shell, epiphallus without flagellum, dart sac small and fused with a large accessory sac, three mucous glands inserted individually around the vagina), and it is supported by molecular analyses also.

Within the genus *Oestophora* three groups of species (*barbula*-group, *calpeana*-group and *lusitanica*-group) can be recognized by the morphology of the shell, which is recovered also by molecular analyses in this work and previous studies (GÓMEZ-MOLINER ET AL. 2013;

RAZKIN ET AL. 2015). However, the relationships between some of the main clades were not resolved and the need for more work to achieve an adequate phylogeny of the genus is evident. According to molecular data, the *barbula*-group occupies a basal position within the genus. This group, with *O. barbula* (Rossmässler, 1838) and *O. barbella* (Servain, 1880), with flattened conical spiral and toothed opening, is distributed mainly in the western Iberian half, from Galicia and western third of Asturias to Huelva and Sierra Morena, with separate areas in Central Spain, Almería-Murcia and extreme NW of Huesca (CADEVALL & OROZCO 2016).

Table I. Samples and taxa analyzed in this study, with taxa, provenances, coordinates (in MGRS system, 1km of accuracy) and GenBank accession numbers. All locations are from Spain unless otherwise indicated.

Tabla I. Muestras y taxones analizados en este estudio, con taxones, procedencias, coordenadas (en el sistema MGRS, 1 km de precisión) y números de acceso de GenBank. Todas las localidades son de España a menos que se indique lo contrario.

Label	Samples	Locality: Site (Province)	Coord.(MGRS)	GenBank COI
O.mariae	<i>Oestophora mariae</i> Ruiz, Arrébola & Puente, 2009	Castril: Cortijo Tabernillas (Granada)	30SWG2088	FJ86479
O.ebria	<i>Oestophora ebria</i> (Corbella, 2004)	Tolox: 1.5km W from El Castillejo peak (Málaga)	30SUF2661	FJ86483
O.prieto	<i>Oestophora prieto</i> Ruiz, Arrébola & Puente, 2009	Santo Tomé: Noguera de la Sierpe (Jaén)	30SWHO905	FJ86482
O.calpeana	<i>Oestophora calpeana</i> (Morelet, 1854)	Gibraltar (Cádiz)	30STF8901	FJ86478
O.ortizi	<i>Oestophora ortizi</i> De Winter & Ripken, 1991	Cortes de la Frontera: km.122 railway (Málaga)	30STF8445	FJ86484
O.tarnieri	<i>Oestophora tarnieri</i> (Morelet, 1854)	Cortes de la Frontera: km.122 railway (Málaga)	30STF8445	MN207263
O.silvae-(138)	<i>Oestophora silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	Catoira (Pontevedra)	29TNH2223	MN207259
O.silvae-(139)	<i>Oestophora silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	Padrón (A Coruña)	29TNH2731	MN207260
O.sp.B.-(104)	<i>Oestophora aff. silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	Arredondo (Cantabria)	30TVN5089	FJ86485
O.sp.B.-(105)	<i>Oestophora aff. silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	Bilbao: Peña Abanico (Bizkaia)	30TWN0485	FJ86486
O.sp.B.-(136)	<i>Oestophora aff. silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	Belmonte: 5km S, crossroad to Ondes (Asturias)	29TQH2591	MN207261
O.sp.B.-(137)	<i>Oestophora aff. silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	Avilés: Castañeda (Asturias)	30TTP6324	MN207262
O.urbionensis	<i>Oestophora urbionensis</i> n. sp.	Duruero de la Sierra: El Castroviejo (Soria)	30TWM0648	MN207264
O.lusitanica-(151)	<i>Oestophora lusitanica</i> (Pfeiffer, 1841)	Maia (Porto, Portugal)	29TNF3163	MN207258
O.lusitanica-(149)	<i>Oestophora lusitanica</i> (Pfeiffer, 1841)	Maia (Porto, Portugal)	29TNF3164	MN207256
O.lusitanica-(150)	<i>Oestophora lusitanica</i> (Pfeiffer, 1841)	Bussaco (Coimbra, Portugal)	29TNE5469	MN207257
O.barbella-(75)	<i>Oestophora barbella</i> (Servain, 1880)	Vilches: Cerro Cuatro Amigos (Jaén)	30SVH6021	FJ86476
O.barbella-(146)	<i>Oestophora barbella</i> (Servain, 1880)	Jasa: 5km SW (km.39, A-2905) (Huesca)	30TXN8727	MN207255
O.barbella-(144)	<i>Oestophora barbella</i> (Servain, 1880)	Bussaco (Coimbra, Portugal)	29TNE5469	MN207253
O.barbella-(145)	<i>Oestophora barbella</i> (Servain, 1880)	Bayona (Pontevedra)	29TNG2962	MN207254
Caracollina	<i>Caracollina lenticula</i> (Férussac, 1821)	Setcases (Girona)	31TDG4290	AY546265*
Trissexodon	<i>Trissexodon constrictus</i> (Boubée, 1836)	Bilbao: Monte Pagasarri (Bizkaia)	30TWN0486	FJ86497

* Published by STEINKE, ALBRECHT & PFENNINGER (2004) and downloaded from GenBank

The *calpeana*-group, with somewhat conical spire, peripheral angulosity and edentate opening, which includes species restricted to Andalusia [*O. calpeana* (Morelet, 1854), *O. tarnieri* (Morelet, 1854), *O. dorotheae* Hesse, 1930, *O. ortizi* De Winter & Ripken, 1991, *O. granesae* Arrébola, 1998, *O. mariae* Ruiz, Arrébola

& Puente, 2008 and *O. prieto* Ruiz, Arrébola & Puente, 2008]. This study did not resolve relationships within this group and further molecular studies will be necessary to elucidate the phylogenetic relationships between these species.

Finally, the *lusitanica*-group, with flattened shell without peripheral angu-

Figure 9. Phylogeny of the genus *Oestophora* by Bayesian inference on the concatenated mitochondrial dataset. The coloured four clades (blue, light and dark green and red) are confronted with their Iberian ranges. See Table I for taxa, provenances, coordinates and GenBank accession numbers. Branches of outgroup taxa are cut in half length to avoid their long branches.

Figura 9. Filogenia del género *Oestophora* por inferencia bayesiana en el conjunto de datos mitocondriales concatenados. Los cuatro clados de colores (azul, verde claro y oscuro y rojo) se confrontan a sus rangos ibéricos. Ver la Tabla I para taxones, procedencias, coordenadas y números de acceso a GenBank. Las ramas de los taxones externos están recortadas a la mitad de su longitud para evitar sus ramas largas.

losity and lunate opening, which includes the species of the northwestern part of Iberia (*O. lusitanica* and *O. silvae*) and to which *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp. belongs too. *O. lusitanica*, with limited distribution to the northern half of Portugal, Galicia and the contiguous region of Asturias, is usually differentiated by the larger shell size (12-17 mm in diameter). *O. silvae*, with a similar size (CASTILLEJO 1981: 10-11.3 mm, PRIETO 1986: 8.7-11.8 mm) and a geographical

distribution from Galicia to Bizkaia and northern Alava (CADEVALL & OROZCO 2016), is the closest species. ORTIZ DE ZARATE (1962) described it from Bayona (Galicia, Spain) but also quoted it from several places in Cantabria. However, the comparison with *O. silvae* is complex because both PRIETO (1986) and PUENTE (1996) indicate the existence of two taxa hidden under that name, a western taxon in Galicia, thus bearing the name *O. silvae*, and an eastern one in Bizkaia,

Cantabria and Asturias (*Oestophora* sp. B). The differences between both and *O. urbionensis* n. sp. are subtle; the shell of the Basque-Cantabrian form, geographically closer, is reddish brown and fairly more solid, and lacks a callus behind the opening while the shell of *O. urbionensis* n. sp. is light brown and less calcified. Regarding the genital tract, *O. silvae* presents mucous glands, bursa copulatrix and oviduct shorter, and a greater penis/epiphallus ratio, while *O. urbionensis* n. sp. presents a longer and more robust dart sac complex than *O. silvae* and *O. sp. B*. Molecular methods differentiate clearly these two forms. However, the relationship and status of these two taxa should be studied more deeply in the future, pointing out zones of geographic closeness and contact (if exists) and confirm the existence of a geographical gap between Asturian and Basque-Cantabrian populations.

The presence of *Oestophora urbionensis* n. sp. in the lower limit of the oromediterranean belt, in a mountain pine

forest (habitat which practically disappeared from the Cantabrian area during the Subatlantic period, less than 2500 years ago; ARRIBAS 2004) and in a very peculiar and relatively unsuitable geological substrate, is surprising. Other closer species as *Oestophora silvae* inhabit up to 700 m a.s.l. (CADEVALL & OROZCO 2016), while *O. urbionensis* n. sp. dwells much higher (1500 m a.s.l.) and in a fairly harsh climate and continental area. Relict species with pronounced hydrophilicity such as *Helicodonta obvoluta* or *Elona quimperiana* are associated in the northern Iberian System with *Fagus sylvatica* forests (PRIETO 1986; ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE 1991; ARRIBAS 1992; ALTONAGA *ET AL.* 1994) and have probably survived in micro-refuges of this species or arrived with this forest during its recent Holocene expansion. *Fagus sylvatica* appeared in Quintanar de la Sierra (in the Burgos part of Picos de Urbión, as late as 3000 years ago; ARRIBAS 2004). The presence of *O. urbionensis* n. sp. therefore seems to be old and relictual.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AHUIR GALINDO J. & TORRES ALBA J.S. 2017. Six new terrestrial gastropod species from Morocco (Gastropoda: Chondrinidae, Trissexodontidae). *Malacologia Mostra Mondiale*, 96, 8-12.
- AKAIKE H. 1974. A new look at the statistical model identification. *IEEE transactions on automatic control*, 19 (6), 716-723.
- ALTABA C.R. 2007. A new land snail from the Quaternary of Mallorca (Balearic Islands, Western Mediterranean): *Darderia bellverica* n. gen., n. sp. (Gastropoda Pulmonata, Helicodontidae). *Animal Biodiversity and Conservation*, 29 (2) (2006), 195-200.
- ALTONAGA K., GÓMEZ B., MARTÍN R., PRIETO C.E., PUENTE A.I. & RALLO A. 1994. *Estudio faunístico y biogeográfico de los moluscos terrestres del norte de la Península Ibérica*. Ed. Parlamento Vasco. 503 pp.
- ARNÁEZ-VADILLO J. 1987. Formas y procesos en la evolución de vertientes de la Sierra de la Demanda (Sistema Ibérico). *Cuadernos de Investigación Geográfica*, 13, 7-153. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18172/cig.962>.
- ARRÉBOLA J.R., PRIETO C.E., PUENTE A.I. & RUIZ Z.A. 2006. *Hatumia*, a new genus for *Oestophora riffensis* Ortiz de Zárate, 1962, *Oestophora cobosi* Ortiz de Zárate, 1962 and *Hatumia pseudogasulli* n. sp. (Pulmonata: Helicoidea: Trissexodontidae). *Journal of Conchology*, 39 (2), 119-134.
- ARRIBAS O. J. 1992. *Elona quimperiana* (Férussac, 1821) en el Sistema Ibérico Septentrional (Gastropoda, Pulmonata, Xanthonychidae). *Zubia*, 10: 25-29.
- ARRIBAS O.J. 1994. Catálogo de los coleópteros caraboideos del Sistema Ibérico Septentrional (Sierras de la Demanda, Cameros, Neila, Urbión y Cebollera). *Zubia Monográfico*, 6, 11-70.
- ARRIBAS O.J. 2004. *Fauna y paisaje de los Pirineos en la Era Glacial*. Lynx Promocions, Barcelona, 540 pp.
- BACKHUYS W. 1975. *Zoogeography and Taxonomy of the land and fresh-water Molluscs of the Azores*. Ed. Backhuys & Meesters, Amsterdam. 350 pp. + 97 map. + 32 pl.

- BANK R.A., BOUCHET P.H., FALKNER G., GITTENBERGER G., HAUSDORF B., VON PROSCHWITZ T. & RIPKEN T.E.J. 2001. Supraspecific classification of European non-marine Mollusca (CLECOM Sections I+II). *Heldia*, 4 (1/2), 77-128.
- CADEVALL J. & OROZCO A. 2016. *Caracoles y babosas de la Península Ibérica y Baleares*. Ed. Omega. Barcelona. 817 pp.
- CASTILLEJO J. 1981. *Los moluscos terrestres de Galicia (Subclase Pulmonata)*. Tesis Doctoral (no publicada). Universidad de Santiago. 499 pp.
- DARRIBA D., TABOADA G.L., DOALLO R., & POSADA D. 2012. jModelTest 2: more models, new heuristics and parallel computing. *Nature methods*, 9 (8), 772.
- ESU D. 1978. La malacofauna continentale plio-pleistocenica della formazione fluvio-lacustre di Nuraghe Su Casteddu (Sardegna orientale) e sue implicazioni paleogeografiche. *Geologica Romana*, 17, 1-34
- GARCÍA DE CELIS A., ARROYO-PÉREZ P. & GANDÍA-FERNÁNDEZ A. 2008. Cambios recientes del límite superior del bosque en Urbión: gestión forestal, ganadería y clima. *Zubía Monográfico*, 20, 97-118.
- GARCÍA-RUIZ J.M., ORTIGOSA L., PELLICER F. & ARNÁEZ J. 1998. Geomorfología glacial del Sistema Ibérico. In Gómez Ortiz A. & Pérez Alberti A. (Eds.): *Las huellas glaciares de las montañas españolas*, Universidad de Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, pp. 347-381.
- GÓMEZ-MOLINER B.J., ELEJALDE A.M., ARRÉBOLA J.R., PUENTE A.I., MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ A., RUIZ A., & MADEIRA M.J. 2013. Molecular phylogeny of the Helicodontidae and Trissexodontidae (Gastropoda). *Zoologica Scripta*, 42 (2), 170-181.
- HOLYOAK D.T. & HOLYOAK G.A. 2012. A taxonomic revision of *Oestophora barbula* (Rossmässler, 1838) and *O. barbella* (Servain, 1880), two Iberian endemic land-snail species (Gastropoda: Trissexodontidae). *Iberus*, 30 (1), 15-40
- HOLYOAK D.T., HOLYOAK G.A. & MENDES R.M.C. 2019. A revised check-list of the land and freshwater Mollusca (Gastropoda and Bivalvia) of mainland Portugal. *Iberus*, 37 (1): 113-168
- HOVESTADT A. & RIPKEN T.E.J. 2015 A new *Oestophora* (Gastropoda, Eupulmonata, Trissexodontidae) from Ilha da Berlenga, Portugal. *Basteria*, 79 (1-3): 30-31
- IGME 1986. *Mapa Geológico de España E. 1:50.000. Hoja 316 (21-13). Quintanar de la Sierra*. Ministerio de Industria y Energía. 51pp + mapa. [<http://info.igme.es/cartografiadigital/geologica/Magna50Hoja.aspx?language=es&id=316>].
- KATOH K., MISAWA K., KUMA K.I., & MIYATA T. 2002. MAFFT: a novel method for rapid multiple sequence alignment based on fast Fourier transform. *Nucleic acids research*, 30 (14), 3059-3066.
- MILLER M.A., PFEIFFER W., & SCHWARTZ T. 2010. Creating the CIPRES Science Gateway for inference of large phylogenetic trees. *SC10 Workshop on Gateway Computing Environments (GCE10)*, 1-8.
- NORDSIECK H. 1987. Revision des systems der Helicoidea. *Archiv fur Molluskenkunde*, 118 (1/3), 9-50.
- ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE A. 1962. Observaciones anatómicas y posición sistemática de varios helicidos españoles. V. Género *Oestophora* Hesse, 1907. *Boletín de la Real Sociedad española de Historia natural (Biología)*, 60, 81-104.
- ORTIZ DE ZÁRATE A. 1991. *Descripción de los moluscos terrestres del valle del Najerilla*. Ed. Gobierno de La Rioja. Logroño. 400 pp.
- PAUL C.R.C. 1984. Pleistocene non-marine molluscs from Cova de Ca Na Reia, Eivissa. *Bolletí de la Societat d'Història Natural de les Balears*, 28, 95-114
- PRIETO C.E. 1986. *Estudio sistemático y biogeográfico de los Helicidae sensu Zilch, 1959-60 (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Stylommatophora) del País Vasco y regiones adyacentes*. Ph.D. Dissertation, University of the Basque Country, Spain [In Spanish]. 393 pp + 10 lám.
- PRIETO C.E., PUENTE A.I., ALTONAGA K. & GÓMEZ B.J. 1993. Genital morphology of *Caracollina lenticula* (Michaud, 1831), with a new proposal of classification of Helicodontoid genera (Pulmonata: Hygromioidea). *Malacologia*, 35 (1), 63-77.
- PUENTE A.I. 1996. El género *Oestophora* Hesse 1907 en la Península Ibérica e Islas Baleares (Gastropoda: Pulmonata: Hygromiidae: Trissexodontinae). *Archiv fur Molluskenkunde*, 126 (1/2): 81-107.
- RAZKIN O., GÓMEZ-MOLINER B.J., PRIETO C.E., MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ A., ARRÉBOLA J.R., MUÑOZ B., CHUECA L.J. & MADEIRA M.J. 2015. Molecular phylogeny of the western Palaearctic Helicoidea (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora). *Molecular Phylogenetics & Evolution*, 83, 99-117.
- REY R. 1974. Notes malacologiques. Gastropodes continentaux et hypohalins de l'Oligocene et du Miocene inferieur. *Revue de Science du Bourbonnais*, 1974, 69-124.
- RIVAS-MARTINEZ S. 1987. *Memoria del mapa de series de vegetación de España*. Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación. Madrid. 268 pp.
- SCHILEYKO A.A. 1991. Taxonomic status, phylogenetic relations and system of the Helicoidea sensu lato (Pulmonata). *Archiv fur Molluskenkunde*, 120 (4/6), 187-236.

- SEGURA-ZUBIZARRETA A., MATEO G. & BENITO-ALONSO J.L. 2012. *Catálogo florístico de la provincia de Soria (2nd edition)*. Monografías de Flora Ibérica, Jolube Consultor Botánico y Editor. 9. 296 pág. + 72 pág. de mapas.
- STEINKE D., ALBRECHT C. & PFENNINGER M. 2004. Molecular phylogeny and character evolution in the Western Palearctic Helicidae s.l. (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 32: 724–734.
- TISCHER G. 1966. El delta wealdico de las montañas ibéricas occidentales y sus enlaces tectónicos. *Notas y Comunicaciones del IGME*, 81, 53-78.
- TORRES ALBA J.S., & AHUIR GALINDO J. 2011. Tres nuevas especies de Gasterópodos terrestres del norte de Marruecos (Gastropoda: Stylommatophora: Chondrinidae, Trissexodontidae, Helicidae). *Malacologia Mostra Mondiale*, 71, 3-7.
- ZILCH A. 1960. Gastropoda Euthyneura. In Wenz W. (Ed.): *Handbuch der Paläozoologie*, 6, 1-835. Berlin.

Appendix 1. *Oestophora* species and their distribution.

Among the species of uncertain validity, there are several north African shells anatomically unknown as *Helix gougeti* Terver 1839, *Helix (Gonostoma) columnae* Kobelt 1889 and *Oestophora wenzi* Pfeffer 1929; *Helix sublusitanica* Castro in Locard 1899, a minute version of *O. lusitanica* from Famação and other Portuguese places, is implicitly discarded from Portugal by HOLYOAK, HOLYOAK & MENDES (2019).

Species	Iberian distribution	Outside distribution
† <i>O. dentata</i> C.R.C. Paul, 1994	Balearic Is.: Ibiza	
† <i>O. bellverica</i> (Altaba 2007)	Balearic Is.: Majorca	
<i>O. barbula</i> (Rossmässler, 1838)	Central coastal Portugal	
<i>O. barbella</i> (Servain, 1880)	Iberian Peninsula (mainly W)	Azores & Madeira
<i>O. lusitanica</i> (Pfeiffer, 1841)	NW-Iberia (C-Portugal to Asturias)	Azores
<i>O. tarnieri</i> (Morelet, 1854)	Cádiz, Málaga and Gibraltar	N-Morocco
<i>O. calpeana</i> (Morelet, 1854)	Gibraltar	N-Morocco
<i>O. dorothaeae</i> Hesse, 1930	Cádiz (Tarifa) and Gibraltar	N-Morocco
<i>O. silvae</i> Ortiz de Zárate, 1962	N. Spain (Galicia to Biscay)	
<i>O. ortizi</i> De Winter & Ripken, 1991	Cádiz and Málaga	
<i>O. granesae</i> Arrébola, 1998	Málaga (S ^a Alcornocales)	
<i>O. ebria</i> (Corbella, 2004)	Málaga (Ronda)	
<i>O. mariae</i> Ruiz, Arrébola & Puente, 2008	Granada (S ^a Castril)	
<i>O. prietoi</i> Ruiz, Arrébola & Puente, 2008	Jaén (S ^a Cazorla), Córdoba (S ^a Morena)	
<i>O. barreli</i> Havestadt & Ripken, 2015	PORTUGAL: Berlengas Is.	
<i>O. urbionensis</i> n. sp.	Soria (S ^a Urbión)	
<i>O. gougeti</i> (Terver 1839)		?
<i>O. hemcenensis</i> (Bourguignat 1868)		N-Algeria
<i>O. maroccana</i> (Morelet 1876)		N-Morocco
<i>O. pechaudi</i> (Bourguignat in Ancey 1882)		N-Algeria
<i>O. columnae</i> (Ponsonby, 1889)		N-Morocco
<i>O. wenzi</i> Pfeffer 1929		?
<i>O. davidjimenezii</i> Torres-Alba & Ahuir-Galindo, 2011		Morocco:Tetouan
<i>O. alexiae</i> Ahuir-Galindo & Torres-Alba, 2017		Morocco:Tetouan
<i>O. carminis</i> Ahuir-Galindo & Torres-Alba, 2017		Morocco:Yebel Musa

Appendix 2. Information about the primers (sequences and reference) of each gene and the complete dataset (sequence length, selected substitution models and their parameters).

Gene	Primer	Sequence	Reference
COI	LC01490 (Fw)	5' GGTCACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG 3'	FOLMER <i>ET AL.</i> 1994
	HCO2198 (Rv)	5' TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA 3'	FOLMER <i>ET AL.</i> 1994
16S	16Sarl (Fw)	5' CGCCTGTTATCAAAAACAT 3'	PALUMBI <i>ET AL.</i> 1991
	16SbrH (Rv)	5' CCGGTCTGAACTCAGATCACGT 3'	PALUMBI <i>ET AL.</i> 1991

Gene	Aligned length	Best model	Pinvar	Gamma
COI	640	HKY+I+G	0.51	0.64
16s	407	TIM2+I+G	0.62	0.36
Total	1047	—	—	—

Bibliography

- PALUMBI, S.R., MARTIN, A., ROMANO, S., McMILLAN, W.O., STICE, L. & GRABOWSKI, G., 1991. The *Simple Fool's Guide to PCR, Version 2.0*. Department of Zoology, University of Hawaii, Honolulu, HI.
- FOLMER, O., BLACK, M., HOEH, W., LUTZ, R. & VRIJENHOEK, R., 1994. DNA primers for amplification of mitochondrial cytochrome. *Molecular Marine Biology and Biotechnology*, 3: 294–299.

